

THE RELEVANCE OF ULTRASOUND SCREENING OF THE BREAST GLANDS DURING PREGNANCY, AIMED AT DETECTING AND PREVENTING FURTHER EMERGENCY PROGRESS

АКТУАЛЬНІСТЬ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВОГО СКРИНІНГУ МОЛОЧНИХ ЗАЛОЗ ПІД ЧАС ВАГІТНОСТІ, СПРЯМОВАНОГО НА ВИЯВЛЕННЯ ТА ЗАПОБІГАННЯ ПОДАЛЬШОГО ПРОГРЕСУВАННЯ РАКУ МОЛОЧНИХ ЗАЛОЗ В ПІСЛЯПОЛОГОВОМУ ПЕРІОДІ

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Relevance of the topic: breast cancer (BC) is the most common cancer (CR) among women. According to the latest global estimates of the International Agency for Research on Cancer, in 2020 the number of new cases of BC exceeded the number of new cases of lung CR in the world. In 2020, BC was diagnosed in 2.3 million women worldwide and caused about 685 thousand deaths. It was the most common cause of death from CR in women and the fifth most common cause of death from CR in general.

According to the National Cancer Registry, in 2020, 12,164 women became ill with BC in Ukraine and 5,156 died, so 4 deaths from it were registered for every 10 new cases. Every 43 minutes in Ukraine one woman is diagnosed with BC, every 1.5 hours - 1 woman dies from it.

Purpose: justification for the introduction of mandatory screening for an ultrasound of the breast at 11-13 and 30 weeks of pregnancy (prg).

Materials and methods of research: the data of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine and the World Health Organization on the incidence of BC in the population of Ukraine and the world were analyzed.

The results of the study: considering the study of L.H. Smith and co-authors (as early as 2001) showed that the frequency of prg (n= 168 911) complicated by malignant neoplasms is: 587 CR diagnosed prenatally (18/100 thousand), 462 CR diagnosed during childbirth (15/100 000), 1198 CR diagnosed in the postpartum period (38/100 000). In women <30 years of age, the prevalence of BC is 9,725.6%. The Danish Registry (2020) records an increase in the proportion of prg -related CR from 5.4 (n=572) to 8.3% (n=1052) over 30 years.

According to an Australian study on prg-related CR, 499 cases of prg -related and 1,299 cases of postpartum prg have been reported over 14 years, with an estimated 137.3 per 100,000 prg. There is a significant increase in the proportion of malignancies associated with prg, which is only 14% can be attributed to an increase in the number of mothers over the age of 35 (from 13.2 to 23.6%).

Data on the postpartum period (up to 12 months after delivery) were included in this study due to the delay in diagnosis during prg and due to insufficient educational work before it.

Conclusions: Given that BC is the first in the world in the incidence of malignant tumors in women, and is the most common CR during prg, it is recommended to perform an ultrasound at 11-13 and 30 weeks of prg to prevent significant progression and complications in the postpartum and long-term period.